

<p>Imrul Alam Kayes Sarkar. THE INDIAN PARTITION LITERATURE Authorspress: New Delhi. 2018. ISBN: 978-93-88008-38-9. Pages 236.</p>		<p>Literature</p> <p>Keywords: partition, literature, novels.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p> <p>The Indian Partition Literature is a book by Imrul Kayes Alam Sarkar who is an Assistant Professor & Head, Department of English, Sailajananda Falguni Smriti Mahavidhyalaya under Burdwan University. His recent published book, <i>The Indian Partition Literature: An Explorative Study</i> focuses on Indian partition narrative. Partition is generally considered as separation of one certain state into two or more units and it is considered as an easy and peaceful division of territory. But this is not true all the time as in the case of partition of India which resulting in the killings of a million innocent lives and displacement of more than ten millions people. It led to the destruction not only of people but of humanity as well. India gained independence on 15th August 1947 but it was divided into two countries; India and Pakistan.</p>		

Introduction

Partition leading to excessive sufferings became the subject matter for many writers of both sides of the borders who have penned down the havoc of partition in the form of various genres and till date this is going on. The theme had fascinated many scholars all over India to carry their research in this field and Imrul Kayes Alam Sarkar is one of them. He has compiled this book collecting 20 research papers written by eminent scholars from various parts of India. The section 'Preface' is being written by Dr. Mandana Kolahdouz Mohamadi who is a Lecturer in Linguistics and Translation Studies in Iran. The first paper by Dr. Manjinder Kaur Sidhu is entitled as "Brutal Annihilation of Emotions, Values, Trust and Relationships in Bapsi Sidhwa's *Ice Candy Man*" discusses the issue raised by Bapsi Sidhwa in her novel, *Ice Candy Man* who is a strong Pakistani voice in fiction. The second paper, "Partition and the Gendered Nations: A Study of Bapsi Sidhwa's *Ice Candy Man* and *An American Brat*" by Dr. Pratipta Shyam Chowdary is a study of two novels of Sidhwa. Dr. Rudrashis Datta in his paper, "Partition Ideology and Narrative Contexts in Rahi Masoom Reza's *Adha Gaon*" highlights the partition ideology as discussed by Rahi Masoom Reza in his masterpiece Urdu novel, *Adha Gaon*.

Arunabha Bose has taken a Bengali novel in her paper, "Epic Melodrama and Socialist Realism: Ritwik Ghatak's *Meghe Dhaka Tara (The Cloud Caped Star)*". Jaspreet Kaur explores struggles and sufferings of women in "Silence of Women in Amrita Pritam's *Pinjar*". Dr. Rishi Ghosh and Dr. Deepanjana Sharma have taken Bengali novels of Sunil Gangopadhyay in their paper, "Bengali Novel in the Pangs of Partition and Uprooted States: With a Special Focus on Selected Novels of Sunil Gangopadhyay". In his paper, "Recalling the Historical Past and Its Effect on Familial Life: A Study of Anita Desai's *Clear Light of the Day*", Basabi Pal has depicted the effect of partition on a family in Anita Desai's novel. Sandip Dolui has taken Khushwant Singh's novel and depicted the trauma of holocaust in "Train to Pakistan: A Literary Representation of Communal Violence after Partition in 1947".

Biplab Das has analyzed A Fine Balance of Rohinton Mistry through partition perspectives in his paper, “An interpretation of Rohinton Mistry’s A Fine Balance through the Lens of Partition” and Bikash Chandra Mandal has explored another novel by Rohinton Mistry in his paper, “The Fragrance of Partition: Rohinton Mistry’s Rajkahini Revisited”. Dr. Md. Sadekul Islam has taken a Bengali novel, NotounIhudiby Salil Sen in his paper, “Traumatic Perspectives of the Indian Partition in Salil Sen’s NotounIhudi (New Jews): A Critical Study”.

Shyamal Kr. Sahahas compared political trauma as depicted in two novels written in English by prominent Indian English writers, Manohar Malgaonkar and Chaman Nahal in his paper, “Representation of Socio-Political Trauma in Manohar Malgaonkar’s A Bend in the Ganges and Chaman Nahal’s Azadi” while Gopal Sarkar has highlighted the sufferings of refugees in Ritwik Ghatak’s novel, Subarnarekhain his paper, “A Reading of Ritwik Ghatak’s Subarnarekha: A Tragic Saga of the Refugees”.

Though human beings whether it was man, woman or children have suffered a lot during holocaust of partition but women were worse affected by it because they abducted, raped and mutilated. Many of them died those who were left alive were not accepted by their families because of their lost honour so either they had committed suicide or were forced into prostitution. This suffering of women is the theme of Lokesh Mondal’s paper, “The Traumatized Experienced, Victimized Self of Sexually Violated and Abducted Women during the Partition: A Critical Study”. Siddhartha Sankar Ghosh hastaken the theme of love in his paper, “Love in Time of Breaking of Nation in Train to Pakistan” and Abdur Rajjak taken some short stories of Saadat Hasan Manto in his paper, “Penning Pains: A Study of Selected Short Stories of Saadat Hasan Manto”. Writers usually used metaphor to convey various feelings in their writings. Taking this in mind Sushanta Karmakar has taken metaphor of train and village in his paper, “The Representation of the Train and the Village Mano Majra in Khushwant Singh’s Pakistan’s Narrative in Train to Pakistan: A Critical Narratives” and Chandrima Sahahas taken Chaman Nahal’s novel Aazadi in his paper, “Colossal Communal Violence and the Downfall of a Love in Chaman Nahal’s Aazadi: A Critical Study”. Dr. Guruprasad Das has shown how theme of partition is been portrayed in Bengali poetry in his paper, “A Reflection of the Indian Partition and its Consequences in the Bengali Poetry: A Critical Study”. Dr. Shamenaz Bano has taken up one Indian and one Pakistani novel in her paper and highlighted the consequences of partition as reflected by writers from both sides of the borders in her paper, “The Trauma and Holocaust of Partition in Bapsi Sidhwa’s Ice Candy Man and Khushwant Singh’s Train to Pakistan”.

Due to translation of Indian literature in English, now people around the world can read the partition narratives of other languages like Hindi, Urdu, Punjabi, Bengali and other Indian languages. The current book is a fine example of it as we are fortunate to read the literature of many Indian languages like Rahi Masoom Raza’s AdhaGaonis a Urdu novel, Amrita Pritam’s Pinjaris a Punjabi novel and Ritwik Ghatak’s Meghe Dhaka Tara (The Cloud Caped Star) and Salil Sen’s NotounIhudi (New Jews) are Bengali novels. So this is a good collection for people those who want to read notable work in Indian languages. This book comprises of some very fine articles and is good for scholars and researchers working in the field of Partition Literature. I think it is a commendable work by the Editor.